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NEED-BASED LEARNING: AN INTEGRATION OF JUST-IN-TIME-LEARNING, FLIPPED CLASSROOM AND GAMIFICATION IN A PROJECT-BASED LEARNING SETTING

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ABSTRACT

Engineering education must help learners develop analytical, communication, and teamwork skills, alongside independent learning, while meeting ever increasing content demands for solving engineering practice problems. Design problems, typically complex and lacking structure in nature, required an interdisciplinary approach, integrating multiple content domains. The currently most-favored pedagogical models for teaching design are problem-based learning (PBL) and project-based learning (PjBL), both of which are challenged when faced with multidisciplinary open problems, also known as wicked problems. To tackle wicked problems in an educational setting a combination of different pedagogical methods is necessary. This paper strives to create a pedagogical model to use while dealing with wicked problems in the specific education setting of a Master course in an Engineering programme. The behaviorism, cognitivism and situative learning

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paradigms are analyzed and related to the engineering learning peculiarities, which led to proposing Need-Based Learning (NBL). NBL is a pedagogical approach for teaching product design and development, which innovates by integrating Just-In-Time (JIT) Learning, flipped classroom and gamification in a PjBL setting. NBL includes six activities: challenge, select, acquire, apply, reflect, explain, and evaluate. A challenge is set by the lecturer, which becomes the background for all other course work. During the game phases, the students make a 'just-in-time' selection of knowledge to be acquired in the flipped classroom, applying this knowledge in the gamified project and reflecting on their choices and results. The lecturer then gives further feedback and makes the summative evaluation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Engineering education must help learners develop a complex skillset including analytic, communication, independent learning, and teamwork capabilities, while meeting ever increasing content demands for solving typical problems from the engineering practice [1]. Engineering learning and practice have three distinguishing characteristics [2]: (1) use of tools that help create representations (graphs, charts, visuals) to support the engineering work; (2) alignment with professional practices from the engineering community and to work as part of groups and teams; and (3) the emphasis on design, where design has its own unique ways of developing cognitive and situated skill requirements. Design is probably the most common kind of problem regularly solved by engineers, and is indeed widely considered to be one of the core or distinguishing engineering activities [3][4].

Design problems are typically the most complex and ill structured of all problems, and are solved through an iterative process of decision making and model building [1]. Real-world design settings are complex, multifaceted, ill-structured and interact with existing contextual elements [2]. Ill-structured and open problems, also known as wicked problems, normally require the integration of several content domains, that is, they are usually interdisciplinary in nature [1] [5].

The currently most-favored pedagogical models for teaching design are problem-based learning (PBL) and project-based learning (PjBL) [6]. Both are problem-focused, student-centered, self-directed, self-reflective, and require learning contexts that inspire the students' learning interests, encouraging them to actively participate and discuss [1] [5]. Design teaching and design project management teaching calls for PjBL that resembles the reality, and which normally relates to solving open problems and to the use of multidisciplinary approaches [5], which is a challenge for PjBL [7]. Multidisciplinary open problems require that the problem solver (in this case the students) has existing mental models related to each discipline, in addition to the mental models needed for working collaboratively and combining the disciplines [8]. So, the team members must identify and negotiate candidate approaches into a team strategy.

In this context, the identified problem is to define a pedagogical model that covers the content and the complex relations among its elements in a meaningful way, while resembling the engineering practice reality. Additionally, the students' knowledge level on the included and multiple disciplines cannot be assumed to be the same, which means the course must support each student in learn the disciplines starting at their level and, therefore, avoid the demotivation factor of learning material being too easy or difficult. Solving this problem is necessary to support the students creating the mental models that will help them in future design practice.

Considering this motivation, this concept paper proposes the Need-Based Learning (NBL) higher education pedagogical model for teaching product design and development (PDD), which innovates by combining JIT-Learning and gamification in a PjBL setting. The gamified project creates the scenario (set of specific

tasks/problems) for the just-in-time pulling of learning content, where the students will learn as needed to perform the project.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

As mentioned before, engineering learning and working is characterized by use of supporting tools, taking part in the engineering practice community, working in groups and teams, and the emphasis on design [1] [2] [9]. When solving design problems, the future engineers must use mental models that include and integrate the content relating to: (1) the typical design and development process's phases; (2) the best practices covering the design and development process areas; (3) the different development models (i.e., waterfall, iterative and agile) that help organizing the design and development according to the specific aspects from the solution to be developed; (4) the specific techniques used by the diverse disciplines involved during a particular development; and (5) how all this content must be given relevance and meaning by being integrated during a design and development project. Therefore, defining the design and development approach to be used in a particular scenario is a multidisciplinary open problem, which can also be considered a wicked problem. These problems can have several possible solutions, and these problems' underlying uncertainty and ambiguity require critical thinking and creativity from the solvers [10].

2.1 Paradigms for learning

The three different theoretical orientations or paradigm for learning are behaviorism, cognitivism, and situative [11][2]. In a nutshell their focus is on WHAT and HOW associations among the knowledge elements exist, WHY these associations exist, and WHEN (in which situations) these associations can be used. Historically they have contributed to insights on how cognition and learning can influence educational practices [12]. While each perspective is valuable, they frame the “learning” and “transfer” of theoretical and practical issues in distinctive and complementary ways, where the former is the process by which knowledge is increased or modified, and the latter is the process of applying knowledge in new situations [12].

In behaviorism knowing is the acquisition/identification of cause-consequence associations, and learning is “conditioning”, so that a response learned as an association to one stimulus generalizes/transfers more strongly to other similar stimuli [12]. The teacher gives clear and observable objectives for the student to follow; students are assessed by being able to repeat the taught procedures or repeat the content [11]. Student engagement is assumed to occur mainly in response to extrinsic motivations: rewards, punishments, and positive or negative incentives [12].

In cognitivism knowing is identifying structures of information and processes that allow recognition and construction of patterns for reasoning, problem solving, and use and understanding of languages. Understanding is an active process of construction rather than passive assimilation of information or rote memorization.

Transfer is based on acquiring an abstract mental representation/model that designates structural knowledge relations that are invariant across situations [12]. In the constructivism variant from cognitivism the learner is in control, and the mental models learned are a “construction” by the learner. As a result, each person has a slightly different model that is a combination of all of his or her past experiences and interpretations of the current situation. Problem-based learning often takes this form [11]. Student engagement is assumed to occur mainly in response to intrinsic motivations, so the emphasis is on figuring out ways to foster students’ natural tendencies to learn and understand [12].

In the situative paradigm, knowledge is distributed in the context which includes individuals, the tools, artifacts, and books that they use, and the communications and practices in which they participate. All actions and activities contribute to a larger objective, therefore learning becomes about understanding this objective and aligning collective actions with that [2]. Transferring knowledge requires that some constraints and/or affordances are invariant under the transformations that change the learning situation into the transfer situation. For transfer to occur, the learner must become aware of those invariants [12]. The teacher becomes a member in the community of practice or a stand-in for that community and is a facilitator of the learning process, while the students become increasingly skilled actors in the community of practice. Class activities and assessment include participation in authentic learning environments and solving typical/real problems from the community [11]. Motivation and engagement is based on the social engagement [12].

Some scholars advocate bridging these perspectives, particularly cognitive and situative [12][13], so it is possible to overcome the dichotomy between acquisition (learning is something we acquire, the cognitive perspective) and participation (learning is participating, the situative perspective) metaphors [2] [14]. Indeed, the choice of combining different perspectives can be supported by comparing to knowledge creation in the information theory, where a collection of data only becomes information if the relations among them is understood, and a collection of information becomes knowledge if the underlying patterns are understood. In this sense, data acquisition resembles the behaviorism, and information and knowledge identification have a parallel to cognitive and situative, respectively. In this context, this work will combine aspects from both cognitive and situative, with emphasis in the situative.

2.2 Teaching strategies

The strategy of mixing methodologies in the classroom allows an inclusive class that embraces students diversity [15]. The situative learning paradigm advocates that different forms of knowledge emerge when different materials are involved, so learning is both impacted by the socio-material and the spatial-temporal dimensions of learning. Therefore, mediation by tools and engagement in activities (that include

social interaction) are essential for learning and require understanding the interaction that has emerged over time through reciprocal roles played by actors [2].

In analyzing opportunities to learn in engineering education, learning contexts should be analyzed on how they allow participants to develop engineering-related identities and how they can support the development of positive engineering identities [2]. Consequently, in the case of multidisciplinary design it cannot be done without considering the repertoires of practice that the multiple disciplines' representatives bring to these social context.

Design has its own unique way of developing cognitive and situated skill requirements. It requires skills with materials, ability to work collaboratively, and the ability to become part of a community of practice [9]. Teaching strategies and guiding principles for situative instructional design include:

- Engage participation: students can become engaged and motivated in learning by participating in communities where learning is valued. Effective learning involves being strongly engaged in activities that captures the learner's interest because of their intrinsic qualities, as well as participating in communities [12].
- Create opportunities for active participation in the social and material practices of a target community: learning occurs when students interact with tools, people, and the physical world to develop an understanding of the affordances and constraints of culturally condoned tools and artifacts [11].
- Create a learning environment that allows learners to chart their own learning path: learning outcomes in a situated approach are not specified for each student in advance, rather the project/problem used to engage and embed the learning is rich and complex enough to support the exploration of multiple, self-determined learning pathways [11].

3 NEED-BASED PEDAGOGICAL MODEL

Pedagogical models are cognitive models or theoretical constructs derived from learning theory that enable the implementation of specific instructional and learning strategies. They are part of a broader teaching and learning model [16], where the pedagogical approach or model delivers the defined vision for learning by implementing certain teaching strategies. A visual representation of how the different elements interact is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. *Situating the pedagogical model in the teaching learning model.*

When looking at the learning paradigm and teaching strategies, as described in section 1 and 2, there are seven elements that can be deduced from the literature, which should be considered when teaching engineering education, namely: (1) ill structured/open/wicked problems; (2) multi/interdisciplinary content; (3) group/project setting; (4) different students' starting knowledge levels; (5) mental models' creation under open problems ambiguity; (6) cognitive learning aspects – patterns, intrinsic motivation; and (7) situative learning aspects – social engagement.

Taking these elements into account, the Need-Based Learning (NBL) model has been designed. As the name says, the objective is that the need for learning created by a challenge, which pulls together learning activities. Figure 2 shows an example of how the specific elements of the NBL model can be integrated into an engineering course for a master programme at the hosting university. The teaching strategies listed in figure 2 are a combination of teaching strategies frequently used at the hosting university and deemed relevant to engineering education. Project-Based Learning, Just-in-time Learning and Flipped-classroom provide an opportunity for tackling all seven elements found to be important for engineering education. Gamification provides an additional opportunity to enhance student motivation, socialization and the introduction of new content in master courses of engineering education [17]. The pedagogical model includes six activities which are common to a design process, and form the backbone of the master course. The activities with a blue background are led by the lecturer, and the activities with a gray background are mainly student driven and supported by gamification.

Figure 2. Need-Based Learning specific elements.

How the **pedagogical model activities** (in bold) and the teaching strategies (underlined) are connected is explained as follows:

A **challenge** is set by the lecturer, and which becomes the background for the game and to all other course activities. The course is based on a gamified project, where collaboration happens among project team members and competition across the teams, for the most effective design process. While going through the gamified project's phases, the students must **select** the knowledge to learn 'just-in-time' making use of the flipped classroom. The phases are based on a typical design and development process [17] and include conceptual design, system design, detail

design, final integration and production ramp-up. The teams strategize and **create** the process (by combining the selected knowledge about the diverse tools and techniques and product development best practices), which they will play in the phase. At the end of each phase, the students then **reflect** on the rationale behind the strategy they chose, the effectiveness of their choices, and what and why they would do differently in a similar future situation. The lecturer then gives feedback (**explain**) based on the reflection. The final activity is to **evaluate** the students' work. Summative assessment is based on the reflections' quality and not on the game results.

Course design under NBL requires first setting the challenge characteristics and creating a game which follows the challenge solving process. The supporting theory must be made available online using videos, articles, wiki pages, etc. This theory is the one necessary for playing the game/solving the challenge and can be accessed as needed. Technology support is only necessary for hosting the theoretical material and the game does not need to be based on software. As an example, Pereira Pessoa et al. [18] present also in this conference proceedings a card game created to be used in a NBL setting, where the compatible challenges are related to product design and development (PDD) and the game is based on the PDD process.

4 DISCUSSION

The NBL was analyzed against the previously identified relevant elements for engineering education, and their coverage by the NBL's activities are expressed in Table 1.

Table1. Elements and Need-Based Learning' activities.

	Challenge	Select	Create	Reflect	Explain	Evaluate
(1) Ill structured/open/wicked problems	x		x			
(2) multi/interdisciplinary content	x	x	x	x	x	
(3) group/project setting		x	x	x		
(4) different students' starting knowledge levels;		x				
(5) mental models' creation under open problems ambiguity		x	x	x	x	x
(6) cognitive learning aspects – patterns, intrinsic motivation	x	x	x	x		
(7) situative learning aspects – social engagement		x	x	x		

The pedagogical model's activities and the choice of teaching strategies were those that supported tackling the elements of NBL. By combining teaching strategies it allows attention to be paid to different types of students and their learning in the class. Since gamification is a methodology that is mixed with other pedagogical tools (project-based learning, flipped classroom, master class, problems, gamified learning, etc.), it accommodates students with diverse backgrounds [15]. The different NBL elements are addressed as following:

- 1) Ill structured/open/wicked problems: the problems are covered by the initial problem, and by the gamified project, which allows different valid approaches to handle the intrinsic game uncertainty.
- 2) multi/interdisciplinary content: the challenge poses the need of this content to be used during the game and is the base for the student's reflection and the lecturer feedback.
- 3) group/project setting: the gamified project is a group project.

- 4) different students' starting knowledge levels: the gamification setting, and the flipped classroom supports the students approaching the theoretical content according to their level and interests.
- 5) mental models' creation under open problems ambiguity: the gamification allows experimenting different choices, which further receive formative and summative feedback. The cycle from selecting->creating->reflecting->feedback supports the mental models' creation.
- 6) cognitive learning aspects – patterns, intrinsic motivation: motivation is based on the gamification setting, which brings a dynamic more in-line with the students' interests and based on bringing a reality-based challenge. Learning patterns takes place during the decision making in the gamified project phases.
situative learning aspects – social engagement: once the challenge requires the expertise on multiple disciplines and the group project setting creates a community, the students learn from collaborating while solving one specific engineering design and development challenge.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This concept paper shows the development of the Need-Based Learning (NBL) pedagogical model, with the motivation of overcoming the challenges for including the and making sense among the extensive multidisciplinary content required to teaching design and development in a project setting that resembles real problems. NBL integrates the cognitive and situative learning paradigms, and combines five pedagogical methods (challenge-based learning, gamification, flipped classroom, just-in-time learning and project-based learning) into six pedagogical activities. Three of these pedagogical activities (challenge, explain and evaluate) are led by the lecturer, and the other three (select, create and reflect) are student driven.

The NBL was empirically validated by cross-checking and reflecting on its coverage of the relevant elements for engineering education identified during the literature review. The results, although promising, are limited by the lack of practical NBL application. Therefore, further research is still necessary to validate the NBL concept in real courses.

This concept paper shows the development of a new pedagogical method (Need-Based Learning), starting from a literature review about the learning paradigm and teaching strategies. Then the outcome of the literature review is connected to the vision of learning of the hosting university and the important elements are related to activities typical for engineering education. The next step would be to try out the pedagogical model in a real master course for engineering education.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. H. Jonassen, "Engineers as problem solvers," in *Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research*, 2015.

- [2] A. Johri *et al.*, “Situating engineering learning: Bridging engineering education research and the learning sciences,” *J. Eng. Educ.*, 2011, doi: 10.1002/j.2168-9830.2011.tb00007.x.
- [3] H. A. Simon, *The sciences of the artificial*, vol. 1. 1996.
- [4] J. E. Mills and D. F. Treagust, “Engineering Education- is Problem Based or Project-Based Learning the Answer?,” *Australas. J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 3, p. ISSN 1324-5821, 2003, [Online]. Available: http://www.aaee.com.au/journal/2003/mills_treagust03.pdf.
- [5] J. L. Polman, “Activity structures for project-based teaching & learning: Design and adaptation of cultural tools,” 1998.
- [6] A. Kolmos, J. E. Holgaard, and N. R. Clausen, “Progression of student self-assessed learning outcomes in systemic PBL,” *Eur. J. Eng. Educ.*, 2020, doi: 10.1080/03043797.2020.1789070.
- [7] C. L. Dym, A. Agogino, O. Eris, D. D. Frey, L. J. Leifer, and H. M. College, “Engineering design thinking , teaching , and learning,” *J. Eng. Educ.*, no. January, pp. 103–120, 2005, doi: 10.1109/EMR.2006.1679078.
- [8] S. Schrader, W. M. Riggs, and R. P. Smith, “Choice over uncertainty and ambiguity in technical problem solving,” *J. Eng. Technol. Manag.*, vol. 10, no. 1–2, pp. 73–99, 1993, doi: 10.1016/0923-4748(93)90059-R.
- [9] A. Johri, B. M. Olds, and K. O’connor, “Situative frameworks for engineering learning research,” in *Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research*, 2015.
- [10] National Academy of Engineering, *Educating the Engineer of 2020: Adapting Engineering Education to the New Century (2005)*. 2005.
- [11] W. C. Newstetter and M. D. Svinicki, “Learning theories for engineering education practice,” in *Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research*, 2015.
- [12] J. G. Greeno, A. M. Collins, and L. B. Resnick, “Cognition and learning,” in *Handbook of Educational Psychology*, 2013.
- [13] S. Vosniadou, “The cognitive-situative divide and the problem of conceptual change,” *Educ. Psychol.*, 2007, doi: 10.1080/00461520709336918.
- [14] A. Sfard, “On two metaphors for learning and the dangers of choosing just one,” *Educ. Res.*, 1998, doi: 10.3102/0013189X027002004.
- [15] A. Hernández-Fernández, N. Olmedo-Torre, and M. Peña, “Is classroom gamification opposed to performance?,” *Sustain.*, 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12239958.
- [16] G. Callister, “The Pedagogical Model,” Department of Education and Training, Melbourne, 2018.
- [17] K. T. Ulrich and S. D. Eppinger, *Product Design and Development*, vol. 384. 2012.
- [18] M. V. Pereira Pessoa, G. J. Wachter, C. Oude Alink, and L. N. Abdala, “Ingenious: an educational game teaching multidisciplinary product design and development project choices,” 2021.